

Contrastive analysis of business and marketing terms in English and Uzbek languages

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Abstract: This article analyzes the lexical-semantic features of a number of terms related to business tourism in English and Uzbek languages. Tourism is one of the important aspects of the country's economy today. With the emergence of new types of tourism, new terms are emerging. In the last century, the terms related to various fields were adopted into the Uzbek language from European languages through the Russian language, and today they are being adopted directly from foreign languages.

Key words: business, marketing, tourism, tourism industry

Introduction: The purpose of marketing is to achieve the company's goal. The main goal of marketing is the regular formation and development of the exchange process, which in turn brings mutual benefit to its participants. Marketing objectives are implemented in a certain hierarchical sequence and include economic and psychographic objectives. The first group of goals directly leads to higher indicators of the company's profit and profitability.

• Professor EP Golubkov proposed the following goal structure of marketing activity:

- Achieving the company's goals by maintaining an effective marketing policy.
- Targets focused on individual markets and product groups.
- Targets, price, sales organization, delivery to the consumer in effective ways directed at individual elements of the marketing complex. In a broad sense, the purpose of marketing is to implement all the activities necessary to regulate supply and demand, that is, to apply new ideas to the creation of goods, to implement effective distribution channels with minimal costs, to satisfy the needs of consumers. meet the increasing modern demands.

Research results and methods: The development of the tourism industry has a positive effect on the improvement of internal economic structures, as well as on the development of industries related to this industry . But it is no secret that large financial resources are required to travel, to rest in a place other than the place of

permanent residence, to see new areas or to restore health in healing areas. These funds are used for getting to the desired destination, overnight stay and accommodation, meals and other services. It is expedient to partially use the state's social protection policy for the segments of the population in need of social protection. In developed countries, systems of organizing special trips for these population groups have been introduced, and through them it is ensured that tourism services serve precisely the underprivileged segments of the population. Tourism is legally carried out by tourist organizations. Accordingly, tourism is divided into several types: domestic tourism, international tourism, amateur tourism, business tourism, ecotourism, sports tourism, car tourism, tourism for expanding the level of knowledge, etc. Business tour is related to the tourist's professional activity, and any organization, economy that brings income, aims to gain profit and is not against the law; type of travel related to commercial, business activities. Inbound tourism is tourism that is carried out by the visit of foreign tourists to the territory of a certain country. Tourists coming to a country are the subject of incoming tourism for that region. Domestic tourism is tourism organized by the permanent residents of a country to the other side of the territory of this country. The term "domestic tourism" has become a widely used lexical unit in recent years. Social tourism is tourism in which travel costs are fully or partially covered by the state budget, extra-budgetary funds, and the employer. A group (package) tour is a tour consisting of a combination of several tourist services. This package includes services such as tour operator, flight, service, transfer, accommodation.

Discussion of the results: As we divided tourism into several groups above, business tourism is also divided into several types: individual trips, group trips, events (meetings, incentives, conferences, exhibitions (MICE), formation of a team and exchange of places during study tours. Business tourism works with many business corporations: hotel chains, organizers of professionally integrated trade fairs and exhibitions, business centers in many countries. Of course, there are separate terms for each field. In this article, we will consider the lexical semantic features of a number of terms related to business tourism in English and Uzbek. is considered Each field has its own terminology. Also, the terminology of tourism occupies a large place in the Uzbek terminological system. In its enrichment, linguistic (linguistic) and non-linguistic (extralinguistic) factors are distinguished. **Conclusion:** Terms and

terminology, such changes have expanded the scope of the Uzbek language and enriched its lexical structure with new scientific and technical terms.

Contract - an agreement concluded between the parties (two or more persons), their rights and obligations are recorded.

Ticket - a document that gives the right to use something (vehicles), enter a place (theater, sports hall, etc.), a ticket.

A flight is a route of vehicles such as ships, airplanes, cars along a certain route.

Visa - a special permit issued by the relevant administrative office in the passport to visit a foreign country, live in it and pass through its territory. symbol _

Tour - organization of transportation of tourists with a set of services in a specific direction and a specific period.

The tourism industry is a collection of various sectors of the national economy that make up the material and technical base of tourism.

Flotel - A floating hotel ship. A huge hotel on the water will be specially equipped. In addition to convenient numbers, facilities are provided for a good rest, use of a temporary office, operational means of communication: telephone, photocopier, fax and other services are provided.

Tourist house - shelter designed for short-term rest of active tourists. These are mainly located on the slopes of the mountains, and the conditions are minimal

Rotel - a mobile hotel, a hotel with one or two-bed rooms in the form of a wagon, a dressing room, a common dining room, and a common toilet.

the two languages, Uzbek and English, in terms of one field-tourism terminologies, we witnessed that in Uzbek some terms are used in their own form, and some alternative versions are used. Many terms in English are given in English. But even in this language we can find words taken from other languages.

conclusion, we can say that creating explanatory, electronic and translation dictionaries of existing tourism terms in the Uzbek language is one of the important tasks of Uzbek terminology. Giving and explaining terms in explanatory dictionaries and special dictionaries for touristic terms serves to familiarize the student with the most necessary and general concepts of this subject and to increase his level of knowledge, as well as to create interest in this field.

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